

A Note on the Minimal Critical Pressure of Explosions.

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In order to explain the variation of the minimal critical pressure with temperature, Semenov (Z. Physik, 1928, 48, 571 ; Chem. Rev., 1929, p. 347 ; Taylor, "A Treatise on Physical Chemistry" p. 1015) has proposed two theories. It is attempted in this paper to point out an error that has crept in the development of the first theory and to show the relationship between the two theories.

In his first theory, Semenov derives the marginal condition for an explosion the relation :

$$\frac{KRT_2^2}{E} = K(T_2 - T_0) = B. e^{-E/RT_2} n_1^a n_2^b \quad \dots (1)$$

where T_0 = the temperature of the walls, T_2 = the temperature of the reaction mixture, E = the energy of activation, R = the gas constant, K, B = constants, n_1, n_2 = the concentrations of the reactants and $a, b \dots$ = the numbers corresponding to the orders of the reaction with reference to the reactants.

From this equation Semenov derives,

$$T_2 = T_0 \left(1 - \frac{RT_0}{E} \right)$$

which is incorrect. The correct expression for T_2 is

$$T_2 = \frac{E}{2R} \left\{ 1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{4RT_0}{E}} \right\} \quad \dots (2)$$

which gives, on taking the minus sign, $T_2 = T_0 \left(1 + \frac{RT_0}{E} \right)$ to a close approximation. This means that $T_2 \approx T_0$ as RT_0 is small as compared with E . It can be so only if the heat of the reaction is small. As the explosive reactions are usually highly exothermic, this

solution for equation (2) has to be discarded. Taking the positive solution, we get,

$$T_2 = \frac{E}{R} \left(1 - \frac{RT_0}{E} \right)$$

to a close approximation.

Substituting the value of T_2 in equation (1) and setting

$$n_1 = \alpha n_0 \frac{P}{T_2} \cdot \frac{273}{760} ; n_2 = \beta n_0 \cdot \frac{P}{T_2} \cdot \frac{273}{760} ; \dots\dots\dots$$

where n_0 = the total pressure at S.T.P.

and $\alpha, \beta \dots$ = the mole fractions of the different reactants, and taking logarithms of both sides, we get,

$$(a + b + \dots) \ln p = - \underbrace{\ln \left\{ B \alpha^a \beta^b \dots \left(n_0 \frac{273}{760} \right)^{a+b+\dots} \cdot \frac{R}{KE} \right\}}_{\text{constant}}$$

$$+ \underbrace{\frac{RT_0}{E} + 1 + (a + b + \dots) \ln \left[\frac{E}{R} \left\{ 1 - \frac{RT_0}{E} \right\} \right]}_{\text{practically constant}} + \underbrace{\ln \left(1 - \frac{2RT_0}{E} \right)}_{\text{negligible}}$$

Thus $P = a$ constant.

So, on the basis of the first theory, the minimal critical pressure must be independent of temperature (the incorrect expression leads to the conclusion that the minimal critical pressure is related to the temperature by the equation $\ln P = A + B/RT_0$ where A and B are some constants).

This also becomes evident by a consideration of the relationship between the two theories. In the first theory the temperature equilibrium is assumed to take place. In the marginal state

$$T_2 = \frac{E}{R} \left\{ 1 - \frac{RT_0}{E} \right\} \text{ or } RT_2 \approx E \text{ as } RT_0 \text{ is small.}$$

Let us interpret in terms of the second theory. The heat of the reaction which has occurred so far is large enough to raise the temperature of the whole mixture to such a degree as to have a molecule

possessing average energy in the activated state. At this stage U , the minimum energy that is expected of a reactant molecule to get activated by a collision of the second kind with the product molecule, is very small as compared with RT ; hence in the equation (derived on the basis of the second theory)

$$\ln P = A + \frac{U}{nRT}, \text{ we can put } \frac{U}{nRT} = 0. \text{ Hence, we get, } P = \text{a constant.}$$

Thus a 'thermal' explosion (as pictured in the first theory) corresponds to a "chain" explosion (as envisaged in the second theory) with a low value for U .

SUMMARY.

An error in the development of the first theory of Semenov is pointed out.

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